

THERAPEUTIC PREPARATION BEFORE PROSTHETICS WITH CERAMIC-METAL STRUCTURES**Yagubova F..***Department of Pediatry Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan***Kalbiyeva N..***Department of Pediatry Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan***Mammadova Ay.***Department of Pediatry Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7437276>**Abstract**

Depulping of teeth before prosthetics with ceramic-metal crowns should be done only for special indications. We have determined the prevalence and validity of depulping of teeth during therapeutic preparation before prosthetics with metal-ceramic crowns. A retrospective analysis of 873 outpatient case histories was performed. The number of previously pulpless teeth, intact teeth and specially pulpless teeth, prosthetized with metal-ceramic crowns, was determined. The validity of indications for depulping of teeth before prosthetics was established. According to our data, out of 1635 intact teeth subject to prosthetics with metal-ceramic crowns, 1377 (84.22%) teeth were depulped, including 1371 (83.85%) teeth without reasonable indications.

Keywords: special training, prosthetics with crowns.

In recent years, ceramic-metal constructions have taken the main place in prosthetics with partial loss of teeth and crown defects, since they allow not only to optimally reproduce the anatomical shape of the teeth and fully restore chewing function, but also meet the increased aesthetic requirements of patients, allowing them to achieve a functional and aesthetic optimum. Odontopreparation for metal-ceramic constructions involves grinding of tooth tissues up to 2 mm, which can adversely affect the state of the dental pulp. To avoid complications, it is necessary to strictly observe the regimens for the preparation of hard tissues of the teeth, to know the safety zones, and to master the methods of local anesthesia. One of the main conditions is also the adoption of measures to protect the prepared tooth from temperature and chemical influences and the penetration of infection through open dentinal tubules. All this requires a highly qualified orthopedist-stomatologist, additional time costs, high-tech equipment and modern materials. In some cases, as part of a special therapeutic preparation of teeth, it becomes necessary to depulp them before prosthetics. Indications for such preparation of teeth have long been formulated and defined. According to various authors [1, 3, 5, 7], therapeutic preparation in the form of depulping of teeth is an extreme measure that should be taken in the following cases: - if a wide tooth cavity is determined radiographically, the tooth may be opened during preparation or a thin layer will remain after preparation dentin, unable to protect the pulp; - with dentoalveolar elongation or protrusion of teeth > 5 mm; - with position anomalies, tooth inclination >15°, rotation of the central incisors of the upper jaw >30° and lateral incisors >50°; - in patients with periodontitis, when splinting the teeth of the

anterior group, if a decision has been made to significantly shorten the crowns of the teeth; - with pathological abrasion of teeth II and III degree; - in case of persistent hyperesthesia after tooth preparation, which does not disappear after conservative treatment; - in cases of significant destruction of the crowns of natural abutment teeth, when a decision was made to restore with stump inlays [1, 3, 5, 7]. According to the literature [2, 4, 6] and our own observations, despite the existence of strict indications for depulping of teeth before prosthetics with ceramic-metal crowns, in the framework of orthopedic practice, most intact abutment teeth are depulped before prosthetics to reduce the incidence of complications and ease of preparation. Unreasonable depulping - depriving an organ of viability - cannot be legitimate both from an ethical and legal point of view. The purpose of the study was to determine the prevalence and validity of depulping of teeth during therapeutic preparation before prosthetics with metal-ceramic crowns. Material and Methods Outpatient records of patients from several dental clinics of various forms of ownership were retrospectively analyzed. In total, 873 outpatient records of patients in whom prosthetics were performed with metal-ceramic crowns and bridges were analyzed. The protocol for the analysis of case histories included the following items:

1. Diagnosis.
2. The total number of teeth used for the support of metal-ceramic crowns and prostheses (previously depulped and intact).
3. The number of teeth subjected to endodontic revision (from previously depulped), the causes of depulping.

4. Number of teeth with satisfactorily sealed root canals.

5. The number of intact teeth subject to prosthetics and depulping in the direction of orthopedic doctors.

6. Justification of the direction for depulping (presence of indications).

7. The number of teeth depulped by general practitioners in the direction of orthopedic doctors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION The analysis of the 1st point showed that out of 873 patients, the diagnosis of partial tooth loss was made in 267 (30.58%); the diagnosis of "crown defect" was recorded in 141 (16.15%) case histories; a combination of these 2 diagnoses occurred in 465 (53.27%) case histories. According to the 2nd point of the protocol, 3174 teeth were used as supports for metal-ceramic structures, of which 1539 (48.53%) were previously depulped and 1635 (51.47%) were intact. Determining the number of teeth subjected to endodontic revision (from previously depulped), we found that 606 (39.38%) of previously depulped teeth (1539) underwent endodontic revision; thus, the number of well-filled teeth was 933 (60.62%). Repeated endodontic treatment was carried out on 606 (39.38%) teeth, including inflammatory changes in the periapical tissues - in 225 (14.62%), due to poor-quality root canal filling - in 381 (24.76%) case. The number of intact teeth subject to prosthetics and depulping in the direction of orthopedists amounted to 1377 (84.22%) of the total number of intact teeth - 1635. At the same time, in 1371 (83.85%) cases, as a reason for referral for depulping in outpatient cards it was indicated: "for orthopedic indications." In 6 (0.37%) cases, the reason for referral for depulping was the presence of changes in the periapical tissues on radiographs. Finding out the reasons for referral for depulping of teeth in the presence of an entry in the outpatient card "according to orthopedic indications", we did not find any grounds for depulping in the section "objective examination" or in the diagnosis. Of the 1635 teeth, 264 (15.78%) were prosthodontized with metal-ceramic crowns with preservation of pulp vitality. From records in outpatient case histories, it can be seen that dental therapists unconditionally depulped intact teeth in 100% of cases after referral by orthopedic doctors. An analysis of 873 outpatient case histories showed that during

prosthetics, out of 3174 teeth used as supports for metal-ceramic prostheses, 1635 (51.47%) were initially with live pulp. Of the 1635 intact teeth subject to prosthetics with metal-ceramic crowns, 1377 (84.22%) were sent for depulping. Changes in periapical tissues found on diagnostic radiographs in 0.37% of cases were indicated in outpatient charts as indications for depulping of teeth before prosthetics. The remaining 1371 (83.85%) teeth underwent depulping "according to orthopedic indications". With the preservation of pulp vitality, 264 teeth (15.78%) of 1635 initially intact teeth were prosthodontized with metal-ceramic crowns. In no case of sending teeth for depulping "according to orthopedic indications" there were objective grounds for this type of special preparation before prosthetics. Thus, our study revealed a significant expansion of indications for depulping of teeth for metal-ceramic crowns, and in the vast majority of cases - absolutely unreasonable. From a legal point of view, this type of special preparation of teeth before prosthetics is illegal in the vast majority of cases.

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